

EVALUATION OF TEAR FILM AND CONVERGENCE INSUFFICIENCY IN INDIVIDUAL ENGAGED IN ONLINE GAMING

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Abstract

Background: Convergence insufficiency are non-strabismic binocular vision anomalies (NSBVA). These are commonly associated with symptoms such as eyestrain, watering, headaches and difficulty maintaining focus nearby. While digital eye strain has been well documented, there remains a gap addressing the relationship between extended gaming duration and aggravation of CI and dryness. **Method:** A cross-sectional study of total 138 sample among NIMS University patients and students. A total of 138 participants (91 males and 47 females) participated in this study. Total of 138 Subject were aged from 15 to 35 years who used Online games on smartphones or computer for at least ≥ 2 hr daily were included. Participants were assessed using standard optometric procedure including RAF ruler, Prism bar, Vergence facility test, TBUT, MEM and subjective refraction. Symptomatology was documented using standardized questionnaire. **Result:** The study revealed that a significant proportion of participants exhibited signs of convergence insufficiency and dryness, particularly those with higher daily gaming duration. CI normal found to be (39.13%), abnormal was (68.87%) which rose progressively with increased gaming time. Statistically significant, indicating that convergence status is significantly related to the number of hours spent on gaming. Tear film assessment shows decreased TBUT. Majority of subjects experienced moderate to severe dryness demonstrates link between screen time. **Conclusion:** This study conclude that prolonged online gaming is often associated with convergence dysfunction and dry eye symptoms. These results support the need for regular visual and ocular surface screening among long time screen user, along with education on proper screen

habits, environmental modifications, and ergonomic guideline especially for those reporting symptoms of eye strain, headaches and dryness.

Keyword: Convergence insufficiency (CI), Tear film breakup time (TBUT), Royal air force ruler (RAF Ruler), Tear Film, Prism Bar, Online Gamer, MEM

INTRODUCTION:

In today's Digital era, Online gaming has emerged not only as a major form of entertainment, but also as a competitive and cognitive activity that demand, rapid visual processing, sustained attention, and fine motor coordination. For decades, the idea of Internet gaming disorder (IGD) has been developed to explain the rise of compulsive online gaming behaviours.⁽¹⁾ One of the primary causes of ocular and physical discomfort is due to the widespread use of visual (or video) display terminals, such as computers and smartphones⁽²⁾. During the era of Covid-19 pandemic, there was a surge in videos game usage, reaching 2.7 billion gamers in 2020, as it provided an engaging, social and safe form of entertainment during lockdown.^(3, 14) As online gaming become more immersive and visually demanding, there is growing concern about the physical and cognitive strain it imposes on the visual system, particularly on binocular vision function, such as convergence and accommodation.^(6, 16) It allows the eye to work together to produce a single, clear and 3-D image. Different image produced in each eye to form single image though grades of binocular vision. The state of simultaneous vision with two seeing eyes (neither of which need necessarily to be normal) that happened when a person fixes his or her visual attention on an object of regard is known as binocular single vision.⁽⁴⁾ Within this system, vital component is convergence- the ability of eye to turn inward for near focus.^(10, 13) Convergence refers to a type of eye movement where both eyes turn inward so that their lines of sight meet in front of the retina.⁽¹¹⁾ This inward movement helps maintain Clear, single binocular vision at any fixed distance. Convergence remains stable throughout the person's life. Convergence insufficiency is an abnormal condition in which the eyes tend to drift outward instead of converging inward properly, which can cause CI symptoms like headache, strain, and difficulty concentrating on near task such as reading or using digital devices. An article stated that sleep deprivation can cause binocular coordination and gaze targets synchronization less stable found that sleep deprivation caused a reduction in convergence for both near and far, especially under high

visual load. ⁽⁵⁾ One report state that during computer work decrease in blink rate observed ⁽⁶⁾ which leads to Digital eye strain. A problem creates with continuous use of screen. Playing video games too much can make it difficult to focus. Compared to staring at digital devices, you usually don't glance away as much when playing video games. Abnormal binocular vision cause asthenopic symptom with continuous use of eyes and may trigger the symptoms of Computer Vision Syndrome. ⁽⁷⁾ Symptoms of Convergence insufficiency and Low vergence facility is observed. Users of digital gadgets, particularly computers, are more susceptible to dry eye illness due to a number of causes. Dry eye soreness and discomfort are believed to lower quality of life and may have an effect on mental health. Activities like reading and driving may be hampered by discomfort and visual problems. Additionally, dry eye may impair productivity at work, which can have an impact on both the economy and individual success. ⁽⁸⁾ Decreased blinking: While working on a visual display terminal, the blinking rate is considerably decreased, even if it is normally between 15 and 20 times per minute. As a result, the eye remains open for a longer period increases the chances of dryness.

METHODOLOGY:

In this article we are conducted cross sectional study of total 138 sample among NIMS University patients and students. The study involved 138 participants, comprising 91 males and 47 females. Each participant was individually informed about the study's objectives and procedures, and written consent was obtained prior to conducting the screening assessments. Total of 138 Subject were aged from 15 to 35 years who used Online games on smartphones or computer for at least ≥ 2 hr daily were included in this study. The following standard clinical tools were used to assess the visual parameters: Consent and preliminary screening participants completed and informed consent form and brief question regarding their gaming habit, duration, screen time and general history were taken. Convergence Insufficiency Symptom Survey (CISS): A validated questionnaires that evaluate the frequency and severity of symptoms associated with convergence insufficiency, headache, blurred vision, eye strain, and concentration during near tasks. RAF Ruler: Used to measure Near point of convergence ⁽²⁵⁾ and Near point of accommodation. Flipper Lenses (± 2.00 D): To assess Binocular accommodative facility. The number of cycle complete in one minute was recorded by using convex and concave lens. Prism bar: To measure negative fusional vergence with base-in prism bar normally range 12/23pd dist. 8/14pd near and positive fusional vergence with base-out prism bar normally range 16/35pd dist. and 14/30 near moving vertically in front of single eye. Snellen Chart for visual Acuity Retinoscope for Monocular Estimate Method (MEM), Trial Set for NRA & PRA. Slit lamp for TBUT.

RESULT:

Participant Overview and Gaming Categorization: A total of 138 participants (91 males and 47 females) aged between 15 and 35 years (mean = 19.97 ± 1.75 years) participated in this study. All were involved in online gaming to varying degrees. To examine the impact of gaming on binocular visual function, participants were divided into four groups based on their gaming duration:

FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF CONVERGENCE STATUS OF SUBJECTS:

frequency distribution of convergence insufficiency among 138 participants. The majority of the subjects (50.00%) were found to have mild symptoms of convergence insufficiency. A total of 54 participants (39.13%) demonstrates a normal convergence function, while insufficient was observed in (10.87%).

Category		0 - 3 Hrs.	3 - 6 Hrs.	6 - 9 Hrs.	> 9 Hrs.	P - Value
A.) Convergence Status	Insufficient	0	8	7	0	0.0008
	Borderline	9	36	22	2	
	Normal	18	28	8	0	

Table 1(A): The chi-square test for association between gaming hour and convergence insufficiency yielded a chi-square value of 14.272 with a p-value of 0.0008. since the p-value is less than 0.05, the association is statistically significant, indicating that convergence status is significantly related to the number of hours spent on gaming.

INTERPRETATION: This graph analyses the convergence status of subject across varying durations of gaming hour, classified into four groups. This graph showing deterioration in

convergence function with increased gaming duration. The number of subjects with normal convergence is highest in the 0–3-hour category and declines as gaming time increases. Conversely, borderline and convergence insufficiency are more prevalent in the higher gaming duration categories. The 3-6 hours group showed the highest number of borderlines, while the 6–9-hour group also recorded notable increase in insufficient cases. This graph shows a possible correlation between extended screen time through gaming and compromised convergence ability.

FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF DRYNESS STATUS OF PARTICIPANTS:

frequency distribution of ocular dryness among 138 participants. The majority of subjects (68.12%) experienced moderate dryness, indicating prevalence of ocular surface discomfort associated with prolonged screen exposure. (3.16%) of participants were found to have severe dryness.

Category		0 - 3 Hrs.	3 - 6 Hrs.	6 - 9 Hrs.	> 9 Hrs.	P - Value
B.) Dryness Status	Severe Dryness	1	20	20	2	< 0.0001
	Moderate Dryness	25	52	17	0	
	Normal	1	0	0	0	

Table 9 (B): The chi-square test for association between gaming hour and dryness status also showed statistical significance, with a chi-square value of 21.465 and p-value of less than 0.0001. This indicates that the severity of dryness is significantly related to the number of hours spent on gaming.

INTERPRETATION: The bar graph presents the distribution of dryness symptom among participants based on their gaming habits. Participants were classified into four groups. The

data demonstrated a clear and progressive increased in ocular dryness severity with longer gaming hours. Subjects gaming for shorter duration(0-3hr) primarily experienced moderate dryness, with rare occurrence of severe dryness or normal condition. As gaming hour increased, there was marked rise in both moderate and severe dryness. These findings suggest a strong possible correlation between increased gaming duration and severity of ocular surface. Hence it shows prolonged screen exposure, as associated with excessive gaming, may lead to significant tear film instability and dryness related symptoms.

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the relationship between gaming duration, convergence insufficiency and tear film stability among online gamers. The findings revealed a statistically significant relationship between increased gaming duration and convergence status ($p = 0.0008$). Participants who played for longer hours, particularly between 3–9 hours daily, exhibited a higher prevalence of borderline or insufficient convergence. Notably, normal convergence was observed in 18 individuals within the 2–3-hour group but declined to zero in the >9-hour group. The graph shows a clear trend indicating that increased gaming hours per day are associated with a decline in normal convergence function. In the 2–3-hour group, most subjects had normal convergence, with no cases of insufficiency. However, as gaming duration increased to 3–6 hours, there was a notable rise in borderline and insufficient convergence cases. This trend continued in the 6–9-hour group, where the number of subjects with normal convergence dropped significantly. In the group gaming for more than 9 hours, none had normal convergence, and all showed some level of deficit. These findings suggest that prolonged gaming may negatively impact convergence ability, likely due to extended near work and reduced visual rest periods.^(12, 15) This trend reflects the impact of sustained near vision demands associated with extended gaming sessions.^(17, 18) During gameplay, players often maintain a fixed gaze at near distances for prolonged periods, requiring continuous convergence.^(22, 23) This visual demand can overwork the medial rectus muscles, resulting in symptoms such as diplopia, eye fatigue, and blurred vision.⁽⁹⁾ The findings are consistent with existing literature which states that prolonged near work without adequate breaks contributes to vergence dysfunctions. Some article also suggest convergence insufficiency associated with sleep where an article stated that sleep deprivation can cause

binocular coordination and gaze targets synchronization less stable found that sleep deprivation caused a reduction in convergence for both near and far, especially under high visual load. ^(5, 24) The relationship between gaming hours and tear film status was likewise statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). Increased gaming time was associated with higher instances of moderate and severe dryness. Severe dryness, which was absent in the lowest exposure group (0–3 hours), appeared in 2 individuals in the >9-hour category. This progressive increase in dry eye severity with gaming duration is indicative of tear film instability likely caused by reduced blink rates and increased screen time. This study finds high number of dryness symptoms across participants which can be due to environmental factor and it demonstrates a strong link between increased gaming hours and the severity of dryness symptoms. In the 0–3-hour group, most subjects showed moderate dryness (25), with only 1 case of severe dryness and 1 normal. As gaming duration increased to 3–6 hours, moderate dryness rose sharply to 52 cases, and severe dryness to 20, with no normal subjects recorded. The 6–9-hour group showed 20 subjects with severe dryness and 17 with moderate dryness, again with no normal cases. In the >9-hour group, only 2 subjects experienced severe dryness, and none were categorized as normal. This progressive shift toward more severe dryness symptoms with longer gaming durations suggests that extended screen exposure significantly contributes to ocular surface discomfort, ⁽¹⁹⁾ likely due to decreased blink rate, prolonged near work, and limited visual rest. ^(20, 21) Blink suppression during concentrated visual tasks like gaming reduces tear film replenishment, leading to faster tear evaporation. Additionally, environmental contributors such as prolonged exposure to artificial lighting and low humidity settings common in indoor gaming setups may exacerbate dry eye symptoms. These findings align with established studies that link digital screen use to dry eye disease (DED), underscoring the need for clinical attention and preventive strategies among heavy gamers. ^(26, 27)

CONCLUSION:

The results of this study demonstrate a clear association between increased daily gaming duration and the deterioration of visual functions, including convergence ability, accommodative facility, and tear film stability. Subjects who engaged in longer gaming sessions showed higher rates of convergence insufficiency and borderline convergence, in line with findings by Rouse et al. (2004) and Rosenfield et al (2016), who noted that prolonged near work is a key contributing factor to convergence insufficiency. Furthermore,

the progression in dry eye symptoms across gaming durations aligns with studies by Portello et al. (2012) and Uchino et al. (2013), which showed that screen use reduces blink rate and increases tear film instability, leading to digital eye strain and dryness. Notably, no subjects gaming beyond 3 hours daily retained normal tear film function, emphasizing the compounding effect of extended screen time.

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